

Collaborative Digital Preservation Policy Revision at Archives Library New Zealand

IPRES 2025
WELLINGTON
AOTEAROA
NEW ZEALAND

Background

National Library of New Zealand Te Puna Mātauranga o Aotearoa and Archives New Zealand Te Rua Mahara o te Kāwanatanga have a long history of collaboration in digital preservation. This includes shared digital preservation infrastructure, and a joint Digital Preservation Strategy published in 2011.

In 2024, members of both organisations were invited to convene a working group whose goal was to develop a new policy to replace the outdated strategy document, and serve as a foundation for ongoing digital preservation work.

Policy Development Process

Policy Principles

We protect and preserve the digital information in our care.

We have a lifecycle approach to digital preservation.

We champion digital preservation in Aotearoa New Zealand, and support champions of digital preservation across Australasia and the Pacific.

We operate a sustainable digital preservation programme through careful financial stewardship, organisational planning, and close consideration of the environmental impact of our work.

Our digital preservation work supports and is informed by our responsibilities under Te Tiriti o Waitangi.

We recognise that preserving digital information is intrinsically linked with enabling appropriate access, in alignment with current legislation, access restrictions, and treaty obligations.

Next Steps

The National Library and Archives NZ now work under a shared organisational structure with joint leadership. We continue to share and iterate upon the policy based on the feedback we receive from new and existing stakeholders.

The Digital Preservation policy will provide timely guidance to the Digital Preservation Team, who will own policy revisions and any operational impacts.

Conclusions

To remain useful and relevant, policies must be aligned with operational processes and guide future activities. The example of the collaborative policy revision approach taken by the National Library and Archives New Zealand provides a case study for organisations wrestling with their own digital preservation policies.